

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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EXPRESSION OF PRAGMATIC PURPOSE IN THE TEXT OF APPLICATIONS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the issues of expressing pragmatic purpose in the text of applications in the Uzbek language. The article also presents the views of several linguists on the expression of pragmatic purpose, and on this basis, a pragmalinguistic analysis of the text of applications is carried out.*

Keywords: *official documents, application letter, pragmalinguistics, pragmatic purpose (intention), illocutionary act, initial intention, resulting intention.*

Introduction. The text of applications, which is considered one of the main types of official documents, can be considered as an object of extensive analysis from a pragmatic point of view. As is known, applications are official documents containing a request, proposal or complaint written in the name of a specific institution or official. An application, as a specific type of official style, includes a text that serves a specific communicative purpose and has a clear pragmatic load. Also, through applications, the applicant (addresser) officially expresses his professional or personal goals, needs, requests or requirements to a specific organization, usually the head of the institution (addressee), which makes it necessary to analyze the issues of expression of pragmatic goals (intentions) in the text of applications from a pragmatic perspective. Because the expression of pragmatic purpose constitutes the main and primary part of pragmatic analysis in linguistics.

Consequently, if we divide official documents that express the pragmatic purpose of specific individuals into several types, we can see that applications are simultaneously types of documents that express the purpose of an individual and the purpose of a group. Because applications are divided into different groups according to the content and the persons writing them. For example, personal applications are documents that express the purpose of an individual, while group applications are applications that express the purpose of a group.

The pragmatic purpose is important in the preparation of official documents, because the intention, that is, the intention of the addressee, is the main factor indicating which type this document belongs to. In the text of documents that have an official nature, the pragmatic purpose can be manifested in different forms. In most

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cases, if the text of the document expresses one purpose, in other cases, several purposes of the addressee are expressed simultaneously in documents with such a feature. It is known that such documents are called multi-purpose or polyintentional documents.

Main body. If we analyze applications based on the above classification, we know that applications are considered documents written with a specific purpose in mind, and are usually written with personal or professional goals in mind, such as employment or admission to study. Therefore, applications are usually considered monointentional, that is, single-purpose documents. However, during our scientific research, we have witnessed that in some cases, applications also exhibit polyintentional, that is, multi-purpose characteristics. Below, we will consider several examples of applications based on the characteristics listed above.

*Marg'ilon shahar davlat notarial idorasiga
Chinoz tumani Eski Toshkent qishlog'i
Samarqand ko'chasi 50-uyda yashovchi
Alijon Sobirovdan*

ARIZA

Men, Alijon Sobirov, 2018-yil mart oyining 22-kunida vafot etgan otam Saidvali Sobirovning merosxo'ri sifatida undan qolgan merosiy mulkdan menga tegishi kerak bo'lgan hissadan Surayyo Saidvaliyevna Rahmonova foydasiga voz kechaman.

(imzo) Alijon Sobirov

Chinoz shahri, ikki ming o'n sakkizinchi yil aprel oyining oltinchi kuni.

This application, which is presented in the practical manual "Davlat tilida ish yuritish" by M. Aminov et al. and reprinted in 2020, is a monointentional (single-purpose) application. Because this application contains the following elements.

First, the main purpose of writing the application is clear, that is, the application pursues only one purpose. This is to renounce his share of the inheritance. Alijon Sobirov renounces his legal right to inheritance and wants to transfer it to Surayyo Saidvalievna Rahmonova.

Secondly, the text of the application does not indicate additional purposes. In general, the text of the application does not contain any mention or additional information about other purposes (for example, demanding financial compensation, concluding an agreement with other heirs, or requesting additional services from the notary office).

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The application is monointentional, because it expresses only one specific purpose (renouncing the inheritance). It is worth noting that if the above application had several purposes (for example, to waive an inheritance and request financial assistance or take other legal measures), then we would consider the above application as a polyintentional document.

Let us turn our attention to another example from the practical guide “*Davlat tilida ish yuritish*”.

*Toshkent shahar Yashnobod tumani Ma'muriy sudiga
Toshkent shahri Farg'ona yo'li shohko'chasi 112-uyda yashovchi Shuhrat*

Mamarasulovich Ro'ziyev

*Toshkent shahri Zomin ko'chasi 15-uyda joylashgan «Naqqosh» xalq
hunarmandchiligi fabrikasi*

ISHGA QAYTA TIKLASH HAMDA MAJBURAN BEKOR QOLGAN VAQT UCHUN ISH HAQI UNDIRISH HAQIDA DA'VO ARIZASI

Men 2012-yil iyul oyidan beri «Naqqosh» xalq hunarmandchi-ligi fabrikasida duradgor sifatida ishlab kelganman. Fabrika bo'yicha 2017-yil 23-oktyabrda chiqarilgan 372-buyruq bilan shtat qisqarishi asosida ishdan bo'shatildim.

Meni ishdan bo'shatishda fabrika ma'muriyati, kasaba uyushmasi qo'mitasi mening ishda goloshimga imtiyozli huquq beruvchi bir qator holatlarni hisobga olmagan.

Men Afg'onistondagi urush nogironiman. Mening qaramog'imda bolalikdan nogiron o'g'lim, xotinim, 65 yoshli onam bor.

Oilada mendan boshqa ishlovchi yo'q.

Fabrikadagi salkam besh yillik mehnat faoliyatim davrida biron marta ham jazo olmaganman. Shu bilan birga, men ishdan bo'shatilgan holda, fabrikada yakka bo'ydoq, uzluksiz ish stajiga ega bo'lmagan yoshlar duradgor bo'lib ishlamoqda.

Fabrika ma'muriyati menga biron-bir boshqa ishni taklif qilishni ham o'ylab ko'rmadi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Mehnat kodeksining 89-,103-,111-,112-moddalariga asosan va O'zbekiston Respublikasi Jinoyat-protsessual kodeksining 304-307-moddalariga rioya qilgan holda:

1) *meni «Naqqosh» xalq hunarmandchiligi fabrikasiga duradgor sifatida ishga qayta tiklash;*

2) *javobgardan mening foydamga majburan bekor qolgan davr uchun o'rtacha ish haqi undirib berish;*

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3) *ushbu da'vo bo'yicha sud garorini tezlik bilan ijro ettirish haqida qaror qabul qilishni so'rayman.*

Ilova:

1. *2017-yil 23-oktyabrdagi buyruqning nusxasi.*
2. *Kasaba uyushmasi qo'mitasining 2017-yil 22-oktyabrdagi qaroridan ko'chirma.*
3. *Oila tarkibi haqida uy-joylardan foydalanish idorasining ma'lumotnomasi.*
4. *O'rtacha ish haqi haqida ma'lumotnoma.*
5. *Nogironlik haqida tuman ijtimoiy ta'minot bo'limining ma'lumotnomasi.*

(Imzo)

Sh. Ro'ziyev

2017-yil, 18-noyabr

We can consider this claim as a multi-purpose claim. Because this claim contains the following elements.

First, the text of this claim lists several goals of the plaintiff (addresser) at once:

- The addresser demands reinstatement to his previous job.
- The addresser demands recovery of the average salary for the period of dismissal.
- The addresser requests the speedy execution of the court decision.

Secondly, the author of the claim cites separate legal grounds in the process of expressing each goal. (Reinstatement to work is based on Articles 89, 103, 111, 112 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The requirements for the recovery of wages and the prompt execution of the court decision are also based on separate legal bases.)

Thirdly, if we focus on the general purpose of the claim, then when writing the claim, the addressee focuses on solving several problems at once. (To obtain a faster result by ensuring the speedy execution of the court decision, to recover material damage for the period of forced dismissal, to obtain a faster result).

In general, depending on the number of issues raised in the applications, the pragmatic purpose of the addressee in the applications also increases, and this serves as the basis for determining whether the applications are single-purpose or multi-purpose.

Also, based on the classification of the linguist O.G. Pochepsov, who deeply analyzed the concept of intention in pragmalinguistics, the pragmatic purpose is divided into initial and final intentions, and in the text of applications, like other types of official documents, the author's initial intention is reflected in the initial intention.

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This purpose determines the reason and main purpose of writing the document and indicates why and for what purpose the author prepared the document. In addition, the results that the author wants to achieve are expressed through the final intention. The final intention reflects the intended result in the process of achieving the initial intention.

As an example, let's consider the above-mentioned A. Sobirov's application on renunciation of inheritance.

In this application, the author's purpose in writing the document is his initial purpose. The addressee in this case indicates why and for what purpose he is writing the application. So, the addressee's initial intention is to express his desire to voluntarily renounce the inheritance. We can see that this intention is expressed in the text of the application through the following sentence: *Men, Alijon Sobirov, ... merosiy mulkdan menga tegishi kerak bo'lgan hissadan ... foydasiga voz kechaman.*

The resulting intention of the author of the application is the legal formalization of the renunciation of the inheritance. So, we can consider the resulting intention as the intended result in the process of achieving the initial purpose. From the content of the application, we can see that this application is sent to the notary office, and the decision to renounce the inheritance should be recorded as an official document and the share in the renounced inheritance should be transferred in favor of Surayyo Saidvalievna Rakhmonova. This is exactly what indicates the author's resulting intention.

Initial and consequential intentions complement each other, making the general content and main purpose of the document more understandable. In general, initial intention expresses the main intention of the author, while consequential intention indicates the result expected from achieving this intention. Also, consequential intention determines the legal consequence that will result from writing an application and submitting it to the necessary office. These concepts are important in the analysis of official documents and help to more clearly express the thoughts and goals of the addressee.

In addition, pragmatic goals can be expressed directly (explicit) or indirectly (implicit) in the text of applications.

For example, in the application sent to the state notary office of the city of Margilan, the initial and consequential goals of the addressee are directly and clearly expressed:

"Men, Alijon Sobirov, ... merosiy mulkdan menga tegishi kerak bo'lgan hissadan ... foydasiga voz kechaman."

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Nevertheless, some elements are left hidden in the text. For example, the addressee does not know why the addressee came to this decision.

From the above cases, we can see that in official applications, the pragmatic purpose of the addressees is expressed directly (explicitly) in many places. The reason for this is that the principles of brevity and conciseness of the official style are important.

Conclusion. Thus, based on the above-mentioned approaches to the expression of pragmatic purpose in linguistics, we have analyzed in detail various cases of the expression of pragmatic purpose in application texts in Uzbek and French, which differ in content. During this study, we paid special attention to how the speaker expresses his communicative-pragmatic goals in each type of text.

In addition, we were able to study several other types of applications within the framework of our study. Although these texts differ in content from the applications analyzed above, the results of the analysis showed that the principles of expression of pragmatic purpose are similar in all cases. That is, it was found that in other types of applications, the addressee's goals, the structure of the text, stylistic means, and the adaptation of the content to communicative goals have the same specific characteristics.

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